

Does Financial Education Improve The Use of Fintech Services And Boost Sustainable Financial Inclusion? An Investigation Using Extended Technology Acceptance Model

Falak Khan*

Amna Farooqui Arsalan

FAST National University of Computer and Emerging Sciences, Islamabad, Pakistan

Corresponding Author: Falak Khan

ABSTRACT: Globally, more than 1.6 billion people are deprived of basic financial services, where this major financially excluded chunk belongs to Asia and Africa. Factors like high banking costs, access barriers and lack of financial education contribute towards the high financial exclusion. Though digitalization, as measured by worldwide high rates of mobile phone possession, can solve many financial and social difficulties, yet financial innovation by itself is not enough, bringing awareness to the use and benefits of such services can have a determinantal effect on the success of global goals of financial inclusion. Unfortunately, slight research has highlighted this, hence based on technology acceptance model this study extends the literature and explores the acceptance of digital financial services and the role financial literacy plays towards its attainment using primary data and applying serial mediation approach in a developing country from Asia, Pakistan. The findings indicate and emphasize the significant role of financial literacy and importance of financial technology. The study additionally investigates the surge in fintech usage during the pandemic (COVID 19). Recommendations for the policymakers are also made.

Keywords: Financial Literacy; Financial Technology; UNSDGs; Technology Acceptance Model; Crisis

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1. Introduction

Similar to any major world event, the COVID pandemic, despite being a highly destructive occurrence in itself, opened up avenues and created opportunities for previously unforeseen business platforms. The boost experienced by technological applications and digital versions of businesses is one such example (Fu & Mishra, 2020). Specifically in the financial realm, the use of Fintech and all that it implies, was seen to be influenced by the fear of exposure to the disease (Daragmeh, Lentner, & Sági, 2021). As COVID spreads through many different mediums including cash and bank notes, during the pandemic's lockdown, accessing cash was also a concern especially in developing countries (Al Nawayseh, 2020).

Fintech, in the period before the pandemic hit, was in varying stages of development and implementation in different parts of the world (R. Hasan, Ashfaq, & Shao, 2021). Several benefits were seen in the adoption of varying types of fintech services, especially the more common mobile payments, ranging from lowering of obstacles to investment and risk taking (Hong, Lu, & Pan, 2020) and improving financial inclusion (M. M. Hasan, Yajuan, & Khan, 2020) to efficient utilization of time (Saad & Fisol, 2019). However, adoption was not widespread due to some reservations about data privacy and security of transactions (Auer, Cornelli, & Frost, 2020).

With the World Health organization (WHO) encouraging individuals to incorporate digital contactless payment methods, the pandemic gave Fintech adoption preference over traditional face-to-face transactions and made it an essential part of daily life where contactless payments became a norm and ATMs or cash payments were avoided to reduce the risk of transmitting the disease and safeguard users' health (Kakinuma, 2022). Further measures taken by governments such as that of Hungary to triple the limit for contactless card purchases to minimize any physical contact with pin terminals further boosted the fintech industry (Daragmeh et al., 2021). The effect was seen through an increase of 24% to 32% in the relative rate of daily downloads of finance-related service applications and also in Hungary, where in the first half of 2020, the online market grew by 121% with an approximate 3.35 million online shoppers in the stated period (Le, 2021).

As per Gupta & Agrawal (2021) before the pandemic, Fintech adaptability was less penetrative as compared to during the pandemic and post pandemic where penetration of fintech was at its peak. Pre pandemic literature presents several factors that impact the potential for fintech adoption (Pollari, 2016); post pandemic literature focuses on how these factors changed in their level of influence due to an unforeseen new factor of fears, perceptions, and risk of disease contagion (Fu & Mishra, 2020).

Mainstream scholarship has mainly examined financial literacy from the financial inclusion nexus (Khan, Siddiqui, & Imtiaz, 2022), the literature on financial literacy and fintech from developing economies perspective is widely missing. Very few studies have explored the relationship with perceived financial literacy as the primary focus (Nguyen, 2022) and hence leaving the extended TAM model and role of COVID 19 in it unaddressed. This study takes inspiration from the TAM model of technology adoption, and investigates the impact that perceptions held by consumers, and their intentions, has on the extent of fintech usage. The fear of exposure to the corona virus disease is taken as a moderating force while how financial literacy affects this relationship, is also seen. The study is based in Pakistan and seeks to clarify the status of fintech usage in the country, so that its potential can be exploited.

2. Review of Literature

The Rise in Fin Tech usage and TAM model

Several factors have been studied as contributors to the rise in Fin tech usage as an alternative to in person use of banking and financial services. Governmental measures such

as financial support and stimulating regulatory environments (Daragmeh et al., 2021) have contributed to increasing use of technological applications for financial needs, especially the use of mobile services for cashless transactions from anywhere in the world.

The theoretically backed behavioral factors of perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use have been studied in different countries and roles, to study how they impact intention, attitude, and usage in consumers. In India, it was found that trust in the security of services positively impacts usage of mobile banking service (Unnikrishnan & Jagannathan, 2018). In Ireland, similar results showed perceived trust to have twice as large an impact on consumer intentions, as compared to perceived usefulness of and familiarity with the application (McGovern, Lambert, & Verrecchia, 2019), both of which also have a positive impact. Perceived usefulness and trust both were also found to positively explain the adoption of mobile banking in a country wise comparative study between Brazil and USA (Malaquias & Hwang, 2019).

A study in Hungary investigated the factors that influence the behavioural intentions of generation X to use mobile payment options and the results confirmed that perceived usefulness significantly influences their behavioural intentions to use mobile payments (Daragmeh et al., 2021). Another study concluded that perceived usefulness is a direct predictor of the user's intention to adopt technology and that there is a significant positive relationship between perceived ease of use and intention to adopt mobile payments (Al-Marouf & Al-Emran, 2018; Park, Rhoads, Hou, & Lee, 2014). Le (2021) focused on TAM theory and adoption of Fintech Post COVID lockdown. The study revealed several findings including the factors that affected the intention to use Fintech during the lockdown which were usefulness, safety, security, and quality administrative service where trust was the most influential factor. The factors that had a significant effect on perceived usefulness and in turn, increased the intention to adopt Fintech post COVID lockdown were the impact of COVID lockdown, security and privacy, trust, and quality administrative service. The study's findings concluded that COVID lockdown has a positive impact on perceived usefulness towards fintech and that perceived usefulness towards Fintech has a positive impact on the intention to adopt Fintech.

Any technology introduced initially faces these behavioral realities of perception biases, before being later adopted; the technology acceptance model (TAM) introduced by Davis (1989), explained how perceptions about ease of use and utility, impact a person's intention to adopt a certain technology, which then leads to stages of actual usage. These perceptions are shaped by several factors, some to do with context of use and relevance, and others to do with experience of the user. Hence perceived usefulness and intention lead to usage. To examine this proposition, this study hypothesizes that perception is linked to intention and fin tech usage.

H1: Perception is positively related to intention

H2: Intention mediates the relationship between perception and fintech usage

Extended TAM model and financial literacy

The multifaceted role of financial literacy in financial inclusion is repeatedly highlighted in the literature (Goyal & Kumar, 2021; Khan et al., 2022). It is postulated that financially knowledgeable people are better at financial decision making where such decisions are revolutionized with the exponential growth in fintech (Lusardi, 2019; Morgan, Huang, & Trinh, 2019). In a study based in Nigeria, it was revealed that financial literacy is a major contributor towards formal financial services' access (Jünger & Mietzner, 2020). In Bangladesh, a country where almost half of the adult population, specifically the low-income group, is excluded from financial access and where millions of people in the rural area lack knowledge about banking services, Fintech, and microfinance, a study was conducted to see the impact of financial literacy and financial access. Results of the study revealed that financial literacy has a positive effect on financial access and that financial knowledge was one of the most influential factors to promote financial inclusion (M. Hasan, Le, & Hoque, 2021). The study also revealed that while majority of the respondents were fintech users, they were less familiar with the services provided and hence, were not utilizing it correctly. This is in line with literature that placed emphasis on financial literacy as a factor to increase financial inclusion (Kodongo, 2018; Morgan et al., 2019).

In contrast, Chan, Troshani, Hill, and Hoffmann (2022) found out that financial literacy weakens the intention to adopt open banking, by lowering trust. In the same study, social influence is seen to play a mediating role between performance expectancy and usage intention, strengthening the relationship. Though not directly explored, financial literacy is also seen to impact intentions and actual behavior for example entrepreneurial intentions (Alshebami & Al Marri, 2022) and financial behaviors (Fernandes, Lynch Jr, & Netemeyer, 2014). Similarly, a study also explored the role of Islamic financial literacy on intentions to use digital financial products (Nugroho & Apriliana, 2022). The better the financial literacy, the higher will be fintech usage as financially literate individuals are more aware of financial concepts (Jünger & Mietzner, 2020).

A sample of 500 potential service users were tested using SEM-PLS in a study focusing on the factors that impact the intention to use Fintech application among residents of Jordan during the pandemic period (Al Nawayseh, 2020). The study revealed that perceived benefit has a significant impact on the intention to use Fintech applications which was contrary to the some findings, as perceived technology risks has been found to have a significant impact on intentions. In the Jordan study however, the perception of technology risks did not have a significant impact on the intention for the Jordanian citizens during the pandemic (Cao, Yu, Liu, Gong, & Adeel, 2018; Ryu, 2018; Stewart & Jürjens, 2018). This may be due to the fear of contracting COVID that reduced the fear of technology risks. The study also revealed that intentions to use fintech applications are motivated by the perceived benefits rather than the perceived risks.

In Vietnam, a developing country, a study was conducted to examine the relationship between financial literacy, awareness, and adoption of Fintech products and services and the results of the study indicated that financial literacy is correlated with the awareness of Fintech products such as digital borrowing, digital lending, digital payment, and digital insurance while also correlating with the adoption of two fintech services namely E-banking

and E-payment (Morgan & Trinh, 2019). A study conducted in the West Bank of Palestine investigated the perception of millennials and generation Z towards Fintech services, their usage intention, and their financial behaviour with the results indicating that millennials have a higher intention to use e-wallet, e-banking channels, and services due to their field experience as compared to generation Z, which mainly relied upon cash transactions due to their lack of awareness of Fintech (Abu Daqar, Arqawi, & Abu Karsh, 2021).

Where financial literacy has mainly been examined from the financial inclusion connection (Khan et al., 2022), literature on financial literacy and fintech from developing economies' perspective is notably missing. A very few studies have explored the relationship with the main focus on perceived financial literacy (Nguyen, 2022) and hence the extended TAM model remains untested. Thus, this study extends the literature on TAM, and hypothesizes that financial literacy is associated with fintech usage directly as well as indirectly through enhancing perception and intention towards usage of digital products and services.

H4: Financial literacy is positively related to fintech usage

H5: Perception mediates the relationship between financial literacy and fintech usage

H6: Intention mediates the relationship between financial literacy and fintech usage

H7: Perception and intention mediate the relationship between financial literacy and fintech usage

COVID-19 as an instigator for increased Fin Tech usage

With COVID-19 being declared a pandemic, and found to be highly contaminable through human contact, use of technology to avail financial services became more common than before the pandemic (Fu & Mishra, 2020). Several banking and financial applications that are referred to as fin tech collectively, have been around long enough to raise the question of whether physical banks will eventually be scaled down to the most basic functions, and most banking transactions will be taken over by Fin tech services (Murinde, Rizopoulos, & Zachariadis, 2022). Even before the pandemic, banks were seeing the use of Fin Tech options for transactions such as remittances, payments, crowd funding, personal financial and wealth management; and Fin Tech was seen increasingly as a challenge to be met head on by the banking industry, or face losing users (Allam, 2020). In fact, financial institutions had already started shifting their focus from physical infrastructure development to the provision of novel and advanced monetary and financial technological applications. Their motivation was the need to provide efficient, quick and convenient options to cash based physical banking and financial services and reap the profitable rewards. Some barriers faced were that of perceptions of insecure data and lack of privacy in the use of these applications, and the need for diversion of resources was seen, towards technologies that improve reliability and transparency, to inspire trust in fin tech applications amongst users (Auer et al., 2020; R. Hasan et al., 2021). Foundational work by large financial

corporations was thus already in place, and an upward usage trend already seen (Pollari, 2016).

This upward trend experienced an exponential boost especially during the initial period of the Covid induced lockdown, when there was extreme fear related to the disease, linked with its uncertain and non-uniform spread and symptoms (Fu & Mishra, 2020). Accelerated rates of contraction and death led the WHO to exhort limited exposure to public places, including banks; as a result, the contactless options of financial services saw a growth in its usage (Daragmeh et al., 2021). In fact, the relief provided during the pandemic by digital technology for financial services, like payments and speedy loan disbursements, revealed the potential of fin tech as an effective tool for not only increasing financial inclusion from the demand side, but also boosting banking technology start-ups in the supply side (Modgil, Dwivedi, Rana, Gupta, & Kamble, 2022). After this initial period, the switch to non-physical availing of financial services through Fin Tech is seen to continue, as perceptions about ease of use, security and usefulness changed during the pandemic (Le, 2021).

Covid proved to be a game changer in terms of common trends, perceptions and intentions, as it significantly altered our way of life and thinking, both personal as well as work related (Fu & Mishra, 2022). Since the start of the pandemic, several studies found increased fin tech usage all over the world (Fu & Mishra, 2020). In Hungary, it was linked to a certain segment of the population, called Generation X. Using the extended TAM model, which includes subjective norms as a factor directly influencing intentions and indirectly influencing perceived utility, the study went on to find that forced social isolation proved to bring about a change in perceived usefulness, impacting the intention to adopt in a positive way. Similarly, the perceived risk of contagion also led to a positive impact on behavioral intention. The results did not show a direct link between perceived ease of use; however, indirectly, the study concluded that if users in this specific age find it convenient to use mobile applications for payments, they will find it useful, and will then form the intention to adopt it. This finding prompts investment in innovative fin tech products for banks and financial institutions, to take advantage of users being ready to adopt these services in the post COVID era (Daragmeh et al., 2021).

In the Netherlands, using contactless financial services options via fin tech is found to be a means of supporting good health in the post pandemic period (R. Hasan et al., 2021). In Bulgaria, pre pandemic usage was low, due to lack of familiarity and acceptance, but during the pandemic, attitudes were seen to take a shift, and potential for extended usage became clearer, implying that this area has room for development by fintech providers in the country (Vasenska et al., 2021). Less developed countries, like Africa also showed an enhanced usage of digital applications for routine financial transactions during the pandemic (Allam, 2020).

As the TAM model purports, Fin Tech usage is a function of the perceptions of users about ease of use and usefulness; these perceptions themselves are shaped by several factors, as studied by Davis (1989). This study found that trust in the quality of technical and administrative service and reputation of the service provider and level of data security and assurance of privacy of fintech apps, together with COVID induced lockdowns, played a

role in the intention to adopt fintech services, which in turn impacts how loyal users remain to continued fin tech services (Le, 2021). Hence where the other factors are common in their link to perceptions about digital technology, this study shows that a new factor, the impact of Covid, in fact created loyal customers, so that fintech became the first option for financial services, rather than the alternative. Thus, this study makes a proposition that COVID-19 fear moderates the relationship between perception and fintech usage. Figure 1 shows the detailed hypothesized model for the study.

H3: Fear of COVID-19 moderates the relationship between perception and fintech usage

Figure 1. Hypothesized Model

Fintech status in Pakistan

Where a continuous evolution in the fintech market is evident globally, increase in business scopes, fundings and diversity is also apparent. Financial institutions and corporations are also playing their part towards supply side solution that enhance financial literacy and decrease inequalities across societies. Pakistan, as the worlds' sixth most populated country, is still mainly cash-based where 85 percent of the population is still financially excluded. Factors like high banking costs, access barriers and lack of financial literacy attribute towards the high financial exclusion. Presently, fintech businesses are mainly operated in the developed cities like Karachi, Lahore, and Islamabad. However, more than 100 million people are internet active users, with more than 45% having broadband access and more than 85% of the population owning mobile phone connections accounting to more than 180 million subscriptions. This high penetration serves as an enabling environment for swift growth of fintech and financial inclusion as reported by Global Microscope 2018 report, in which Pakistan was ranked as 21st among 55 surveyed countries Unit, E.I (2018).

As Pakistan possesses a high potential for fintech growth and capacity for digital innovation that can also contribute towards sustainable development goals, this study becomes increasingly important for the policy makers and fintech institutions.

3. Methodology

Sample and Data collection

The study sample constitutes of bank users; this includes people who have bank accounts and use them for payments, receipts and other transactions. Convenience sampling, a non-probabilistic sampling technique was used to gain access to the study sample. Due to COVID 19, data were collected online. The survey was presented with a letter to clarify the scope as well as objective of the research, here respondents were also assured about their voluntary participation, anonymity, and transparency of the data. The response rate was 78%, where 350 complete and filled surveys were received from a total of 448 sent out. The age ranged from 18-55 years with an average age of 34.32 years, with 44% of the respondents being female.

Measures

The scales replies ranged from 1 as 'strongly disagree,' to 5 as 'strongly agree.'

Perception

Measure of perception towards technology acceptance was based on perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use as given by Davis (1989). The questionnaire was adapted from Das and Das (2020) consisting of 10 items. Respondents were requested to read the statements carefully and ascertain their feelings on a 5- point Likert scale ranging from 'strongly disagree' to 'strongly agree'. Some examples of the statements included are 'I think Fintech apps are user friendly' and 'I think interface of Fintech apps will be easy and understandable'. The total score for the measure was the average of all items, with the reliability measure at 0.70.

Financial literacy

Financial knowledge is used to measure knowledge that helps individuals make well-informed financial choices by comparing several products. It also enables individuals to use numeracy skills to ensure they respond to events and news in an appropriate manner. Adopted from OECD toolkit (OECD, 2018), its score is computed based on seven questions about the concept of inflation, interest compounding, and risk and return. The score ranges from 0 to 7.

Fear of COVID-19

Fear of COVID-19 was a 5-item scale adapted from Mertens, Gerritsen, Duijndam, Salemink, and Engelhard (2020). Examples of the statements are 'I was very careful during COVID-19' and 'I avoid going out in public places during COVID'. The reliability of the scale was 0.75

Evaluation of measures and common method bias

For establishing discriminant validity of all the constructs confirmatory factor analysis was performed, the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy was less than 60% ($\chi^2/df= 1618$) and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity was insignificant ($p>0.01$) and the magnitude

of average variance extracted known as AVE (Bagozzi, 1986), gave confirmation of convergent validity existence. For potential common method bias, we ensured proper confidentiality, also told the respondents that there is no right and wrong answers and requested then to be as honest as possible (Conway & Lance, 2010; Podsakoff, MacKenzie, Lee, & Podsakoff, 2003)

Empirical method

To discern the effect of independent variables on fintech usage, the following econometric equation is estimated:

$$FT_i = \gamma_0 + \gamma_1 \text{Percp}_i + \gamma_2 \text{Inten}_i + \gamma_3 \text{FL}_i + \gamma_4 \text{COVID}_i + \epsilon_i \quad (1)$$

Here, FT_i is Fintech usage, Percp_i is perception, Inten_i is intention variable, FL_i is financial literacy variable, COVID_i refers to fear of COVID-19 and ϵ_i is the error term.

At the second stage moderation is preformed using the following equation:

$$FT_i = \gamma_0 + \gamma_1 \text{Percp}_i + \gamma_2 \text{COVID}_i + \gamma_3 \text{Percp}_i * \text{COVID}_i + \epsilon_i \quad (2)$$

Finally, serial mediation is preformed following TAM (Davis, 1989), the following are the series of equations:

$$\text{Percp}_i = \alpha_0 + \gamma_1 \text{FL}_i + \epsilon_1 \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Inten}_i = \alpha_1 + \gamma_1 \text{Percp}_i + \gamma_2 \text{FL}_i + \epsilon_2 \quad (4)$$

$$FT_i = \alpha_2 + \gamma_1 \text{FL}_i + \gamma_2 \text{Percp}_i + \gamma_3 \text{Inten}_i + \epsilon_3 \quad (5)$$

4. Results

Descriptives and correlations

The averages, variances, and the correlations for the variables are shown in Table 1. All of the bivariate correlations (zero-ordered) swerved in the anticipated courses.

Table 1. Averages, variances (Standard deviation), correlations, and their reliabilities

Variables	Averages	SD	1	2	3	4
Fintech Usage	2.28	1.31	1			
Perception	4.1	0.53	0.373***	1		
Financial Literacy	5.08	1.78	0.271***	0.397***	1	
Fear of Covid	1.90	1.01	0.074	0.359***	0.382***	1

N=350

***p,.001; **p,.01; *p,.05.

Regression analysis

We check our hypothesis applying ordinary least squares (OLS) regression. The results appear in table 2. There exists a significant positive relationship between perception and fintech usage (Table.2: $b=0.33$, $p<0.05$). Furthermore, financial literacy significantly impacts fintech usage ($\beta=0.14$, $p<0.001$); a significant positive relation between fear of COVID-19 and fintech usage ($\beta=0.21$, $p<0.001$) and between intention and fintech usage ($\beta=0.23$, $p<0.001$) can also be observed.

Table 2. Results of regression analysis for Fintech usage

	β	<i>t-value</i>
<i>Perception</i>	0.33	2.19
<i>Intention</i>	0.23	2.84
<i>Financial literacy</i>	0.14	3.40
<i>Fear of COVID-19</i>	0.21	3.07
<i>Constant</i>	-1.34	-2.19
<i>R²</i>	0.141***	

Table 3 shows moderation results, indicating a statistical significance for fear of COVID-19 serving as a moderator between perception about fintech and its usage (hypothesis 3). Additionally, figure 2 captures effect of fintech usage at different levels of perception, moderated by fear of COVID-19; it can be observed that as perception about fintech usage rises with increase in fear of COVID-19, people start using fintech related services more frequently. This clearly indicates that perception plays a very significant role in usage of fintech services.

Table 3. Results of moderation analysis

	β	<i>t-value</i>
<i>Perception</i>	0.16	0.55
<i>Fear of COVID-19</i>	0.77	-1.78
<i>Perception *Fear of COVID-19</i>	0.232***	2.21
<i>Constant</i>	1.27	1.07
<i>R²</i>	0.08***	
<i>ΔR²</i>	0.012**	

Figure 2. Moderation graph

Testing TAM

The TAM model is tested, with results as shown in in table 4 indicating a significant relationship between perception and intention (Model I: $\beta=0.94$, $p<0.001$). The mediation results are shown in Model II, where intention directly mediates the relationship between perception and fintech usage (Model II: $\beta=0.17$, $p<0.001$).

As a final step, the partial or full mediation affect is shown through bootstrapping following Preacher and Hayes (2004) in table 5, as it addresses the power issues through indirect effect mainly caused by non-normal sampling distribution. The indirect affect between perception and fintech usage are statistically significant with the interval values not containing a zero and with a confidence interval of 95%, perception as an independent variable is also statistically significant, partial mediation is reflected here. The final mediating effects of intention and fintech usage appear in table 5, the interval values not containing a zero and with a confidence interval of 95% confirm mediation. Additionally, as perception becomes insignificant for the final model, this suggests partial mediation.

Table 4. TAM

	Model I				Model II			
	Coeff	SE	LLCI	ULCI	Coeff	SE	LLCI	ULCI
<i>Constant</i>	-0.09***	[0.34]	-0.77	0.59	-1.60***	[0.52]	-2.62	-0.57
<i>Perception</i>	0.94***	[0.07]	0.79	1.10	0.72***	[0.13]	0.44	0.99
<i>Intention</i>					0.17***	[0.08]	0.01	0.33
<i>R Square</i>	0.29***				0.15***			

Table 5. Bootstrapping Results TAM (Indirect Effects)

Predictor Variable	Mediator	Effect Size	Boot SE	LLCI (95% CI)	ULCI (95% CI)
<i>Perception</i>	<i>Intention</i>	0.16	[0.06]	0.03	0.29

Serial mediation analysis

The serial mediation analysis as an extension to TAM is employed in the study. The results appear in table 6. The stepwise mediation analysis is given in Model I, II and III respectively. There exists a significant positive relationship between financial literacy and perception (Table 6, Model I: $\beta=0.10$, $p<0.001$). To examine the mediating relationship of perception between financial literacy and intention (hypothesis 5 and 6), we follow Hayes (2015) using Process Macro. As reported in Table 6, Step 2 revealed that financial literacy and perception are positively linked to intentions (Model II: $\beta=0.14$, $p<0.001$ and $\beta=0.77$, $p<0.001$ respectively). Model III shows that financial literacy and intentions are positively linked to fintech usage ($\beta=0.12$, $p<0.001$ and $\beta=0.24$, $p<0.001$, respectively).

Table 6. Results of Mediation analysis

	Model I				Model II				Model III			
	Coeff	SE	LLCI	ULCI	Coeff	SE	LLCI	ULCI	Coeff	SE	LLCI	ULCI
<i>Constant</i>	3.51** *	[0.09]	3.33	3.70	-0.04	[0.33]	-0.70	0.61	-0.34	[0.52]	-1.37	0.69
<i>Financial Literacy</i>	0.10** *	[0.14]	0.73	0.132	0.148** *	[0.02]	0.98	0.19	0.12* **	[0.41]	0.40	0.20
<i>Perception</i>					0.776** *	[0.08]	0.60	0.94	0.21	[0.14]	-0.07	0.50
<i>Intention</i>									0.24* **	[0.08]	0.07	0.40
<i>R Square</i>	0.12***				0.33***				0.11***			

Table 7. Bootstrapping Results Extended TAM (Indirect Effects)

Predictor Variable	Mediators	Effect Size	Boot SE	LLCI (95% CI)	ULCI (95% CI)
<i>Financial literacy</i>	<i>Perception</i>	0.22	[0.01]	-0.07	0.05
	<i>Intention</i>	0.035	[0.01]	0.014	0.06
	<i>Perception & Intention</i>	0.01	[0.00]	0.00	0.03

As a final step, the partial or full mediation affect is shown through bootstrapping in table 7, as it addresses the power issues through indirect effect mainly caused by non-normal sampling distribution. The indirect affect between financial literacy and fintech usage through perception is not statistically significant with the interval values containing a zero, however the indirect affect between financial literacy and fintech usage through intention is statistically significant with the interval values not containing a zero and with a confidence interval of 95%, as intention as an independent variable is also statistically significant, partial mediation is reflected here. The final indirect effects of perception and intention acting as mediators between financial literacy and fintech usage also appear in table 7, the interval values not containing a zero and with a confidence interval of 95% confirm mediation. Additionally, as perception becomes significant for the final model, this suggests partial mediation, where financial literacy improves perception about fintech usage that leads to better intentions towards fintech usage which finally leads to actual fintech usage. Hence, extended TAM is proved here.

5. Discussion

To gain a better insight into how fintech usage can be infused in the society, the study investigated the relationship between perception about the fintech, intention to use and role of financial literacy in it. The study thereby acknowledges the contributions that financial literacy plays in fostering the usage of financial technology, which is an area that has barely received any attention in the previous literature. Furthermore, the study tested the mediating role of perception and intention between financial literacy and fintech usage and found that a partial mediation exists in the relationship. Taken together, the current study is amongst the first ones to feature the role of fear of COVID into fintech usage. Overall, this investigation is an effort to create a better understanding of the combined influence of behavioural factors towards usage of technology in the society.

Further, the technology acceptance model was extended in study and applied to fintech usage (Davis, 1989) by combining it as a unified framework to describe the connections between our main variables. Previously TAM was mainly used in acceptance of computer systems. In line with Davis (1989), perception about technology usage leads to the intention to use, which leads to actual fintech usage. Its extended model was tested by investigating the role of financial literacy in the model, which also revealed significant results. The fear of COVID plays an additional role where individuals who have positive perceptions about the fintech usage and feel vulnerable to communicable viruses such as COVID 19, will intensify fintech usage. This is in line with Daragmeh et al. (2021) where the results confirmed that the perceived risk of contracting COVID19 significantly influences the use of Fintech specially that of Hungarian generation X who have a greater risk of

contracting the virus due to their age and societal role, therefore due to the health threat that they faced, they prefer using Fintech for payments.

The pandemic has given preference to fintech over face-to-face transactions as the use of Fintech mitigated the risk of contracting the virus (Mansour, 2022). Studies conducted in the Indian market also concluded that the pandemic is the second strongest factor that impacts demand for Fintech while the technological benefits of using Fintech is the first factor (Ravikumar, Rajesh, Krishna, Haresh, & Arjun, 2022). Furthermore, the study by (Fu & Mishra, 2022) provided evidence of the increase in finance application adoptions across 71 countries were approximately 3.2 million downloads occurred per day due to COVID.

Additionally, in support of our hypothesis, our examination suggest that financial literacy has a positive direct and indirect effect on fintech usage and this is in line with (Mansour, 2022) which concluded the partial literacy significance correlated with the adoption of Fintech. The findings of the study reveal that perception about financial technology is not just a determining factor in fintech usage, but it also strongly correlates with other behavioural factors and financial literacy. These remarks are in support of prior studies that found confirmation of a clear impact of perception on behaviour.

6. Limitations

There are certain limitations of the current study that require attention. This research is built on self-reported data, understood to have a few shortcomings like common method bias (Podsakoff et al., 2003). However, studies have reported ways to minimize this threat (Conway & Lance, 2010). The study ensures anonymity, use of unambiguous items, establishment of reliability and validity through known measures and use of electronic questionnaires hence preventing respondents from going back and forth to change answers. These techniques might all have aided to reduce consequences of common method variance, as mentioned (Podsakoff et al., 2003). The conclusion is also drawn based on statistical support, hence diminishing the likelihood of common method bias in the findings. However, the study acknowledges the limitation due to the correlating nature of the research design.

7. Practical Implications

Use of fintech forms one of the top-level agenda of sustainable development goals of the UN, especially in developing economies, where the average financial literacy scores are quite low. This study, based in Pakistan, highlights important guidelines for fintech companies and policymakers, for similarly placed developing countries, where understanding the role of financial literacy in enhancing fintech usage is crucial. Future research can focus on experimental studies which can see the impact of financial and digital literacy programs on actual fintech usage.

References

1. Abu Daqar, M. A., Arqawi, S., & Abu Karsh, S. (2021). Fintech in the eyes of Millennials and Generation Z (the financial behavior and Fintech perception).
2. Al Nawayseh, M. K. (2020). Fintech in COVID-19 and beyond: what factors are affecting customers' choice of fintech applications? *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity*, 6(4), 153.
3. Al-Marouf, R. A. S., & Al-Emran, M. (2018). Students acceptance of google classroom: An exploratory study using PLS-SEM approach. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning (Online)*, 13(6), 112.
4. Allam, Z. (2020). The forceful reevaluation of cash-based transactions by COVID-19 and its opportunities to transition to cashless systems in digital urban networks. *Surveying the COVID-19 Pandemic and its Implications*, 107.
5. Alshebami, A. S., & Al Marri, S. H. (2022). The impact of financial literacy on entrepreneurial intention: the mediating role of saving behavior. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13.
6. Auer, R., Cornelli, G., & Frost, J. (2020). Covid-19, cash, and the future of payments. Retrieved from
7. Bagozzi, R. P. (1986). Attitude formation under the theory of reasoned action and a purposeful behaviour reformulation. *British Journal of Social Psychology*, 25(2), 95-107.
8. Cao, X., Yu, L., Liu, Z., Gong, M., & Adeel, L. (2018). Understanding mobile payment users' continuance intention: a trust transfer perspective. *Internet Research*, 28(2), 456-476.
9. Chan, R., Troshani, I., Hill, S. R., & Hoffmann, A. (2022). Towards an understanding of consumers' FinTech adoption: the case of Open Banking. *International Journal of Bank Marketing*.
10. Conway, J. M., & Lance, C. E. (2010). What reviewers should expect from authors regarding common method bias in organizational research. *Journal of Business and Psychology*, 25(3), 325-334.
11. Daragmeh, A., Lentner, C., & Sági, J. (2021). FinTech payments in the era of COVID-19: Factors influencing behavioral intentions of "Generation X" in Hungary to use mobile payment. *Journal of Behavioral and Experimental Finance*, 32, 100574.
12. Das, A., & Das, D. (2020). Perception, adoption, and pattern of usage of FinTech services by bank customers: Evidences from Hojai District of Assam. *Emerging Economy Studies*, 6(1), 7-22.
13. Davis, F. D. (1989). Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and user acceptance of information technology. *MIS quarterly*, 319-340.
14. Fernandes, D., Lynch Jr, J. G., & Netemeyer, R. G. (2014). Financial literacy, financial education, and downstream financial behaviors. *Management Science*, 60(8), 1861-1883.
15. Fu, J., & Mishra, M. (2020). The global impact of COVID-19 on FinTech adoption. *Swiss Finance Institute Research Paper(20-38)*.
16. Fu, J., & Mishra, M. (2022). Fintech in the time of COVID- 19: Technological adoption during crises. *Journal of Financial Intermediation*, 50, 100945.
17. Goyal, K., & Kumar, S. (2021). Financial literacy: A systematic review and bibliometric analysis. *International Journal of Consumer Studies*, 45(1), 80-105.
18. Gupta, S., & Agrawal, A. (2021). Analytical study of fintech in India: Pre & Post Pandemic covid-19. *Indian Journal of Economics and Business*, 20(3), 33-71.
19. Hasan, M., Le, T., & Hoque, A. (2021). How does financial literacy impact on inclusive finance? *Financial Innovation*, 7(1), 1-23.
20. Hasan, M. M., Yajuan, L., & Khan, S. (2020). Promoting China's inclusive finance through digital financial services. *Global Business Review*, 0972150919895348.
21. Hasan, R., Ashfaq, M., & Shao, L. (2021). Evaluating Drivers of Fintech Adoption in the Netherlands. *Global Business Review*, 09721509211027402.
22. Hayes, A. F. (2015). An index and test of linear moderated mediation. *Multivariate behavioral research*, 50(1), 1-22.
23. Hong, C. Y., Lu, X., & Pan, J. (2020). FinTech adoption and household risk-taking. Retrieved from

24. Jünger, M., & Mietzner, M. (2020). Banking goes digital: The adoption of FinTech services by German households. *Finance Research Letters*, 34, 101260.
25. Kakinuma, Y. (2022). Financial literacy and quality of life: a moderated mediation approach of fintech adoption and leisure. *International Journal of Social Economics*, 49(12), 1713-1726.
26. Khan, F., Siddiqui, M. A., & Imtiaz, S. (2022). Role of financial literacy in achieving financial inclusion: A review, synthesis and research agenda. *Cogent Business & Management*, 9(1), 2034236.
27. Kodongo, O. (2018). Financial regulations, financial literacy, and financial inclusion: Insights from Kenya. *Emerging Markets Finance and Trade*, 54(12), 2851-2873.
28. Le, M. T. (2021). Examining factors that boost intention and loyalty to use Fintech post-COVID-19 lockdown as a new normal behavior. *Heliyon*, 7(8), e07821.
29. Lusardi, A. (2019). Financial literacy and the need for financial education: evidence and implications. *Swiss Journal of Economics and Statistics*, 155(1), 1-8.
30. Malaquias, R. F., & Hwang, Y. (2019). Mobile banking use: A comparative study with Brazilian and US participants. *International Journal of Information Management*, 44, 132-140.
31. Mansour, H. (2022). How successful countries are in promoting digital transactions during COVID-19. *Journal of Economic Studies*, 49(3), 435-452.
32. McGovern, P., Lambert, J., & Verrecchia, M. (2019). Mobile Banking Adoption: An Exploration of The Behavioural Intention of Consumers in Ireland. *Journal of Accounting & Finance* (2158-3625), 19(8).
33. Mertens, G., Gerritsen, L., Duijndam, S., Salemink, E., & Engelhard, I. M. (2020). Fear of the coronavirus (COVID-19): Predictors in an online study conducted in March 2020. *Journal of anxiety disorders*, 74, 102258.
34. Modgil, S., Dwivedi, Y. K., Rana, N. P., Gupta, S., & Kamble, S. (2022). Has Covid-19 accelerated opportunities for digital entrepreneurship? An Indian perspective. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 175, 121415.
35. Morgan, P. J., Huang, B., & Trinh, L. Q. (2019). The need to promote digital financial literacy for the digital age. *IN THE DIGITAL AGE*.
36. Morgan, P. J., & Trinh, L. Q. (2019). Determinants and impacts of financial literacy in Cambodia and Viet Nam. *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*, 12(1), 19.
37. Murinde, V., Rizopoulos, E., & Zachariadis, M. (2022). The impact of the FinTech revolution on the future of banking: Opportunities and risks. *International Review of Financial Analysis*, 81, 102103.
38. Nguyen, T. A. N. (2022). Does Financial Knowledge Matter in Using Fintech Services? Evidence from an Emerging Economy. *Sustainability*, 14(9), 5083.
39. Nugroho, A. P., & Apriliana, R. M. (2022). Islamic Financial Literacy and Intention to Use Gopay in Yogyakarta: Extended Theory of Acceptance Models. *KnE Social Sciences*, 329-338.
40. OECD. (2018). OECD/INFE toolkit for measuring financial literacy and financial inclusion. In: OECD Publishing Paris, France.
41. Park, N., Rhoads, M., Hou, J., & Lee, K. M. (2014). Understanding the acceptance of teleconferencing systems among employees: An extension of the technology acceptance model. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 39, 118-127.
42. Podsakoff, P. M., MacKenzie, S. B., Lee, J.-Y., & Podsakoff, N. P. (2003). Common method biases in behavioral research: a critical review of the literature and recommended remedies. *Journal of applied psychology*, 88(5), 879.
43. Pollari, I. (2016). The rise of Fintech opportunities and challenges. *Jassa*(3), 15-21.
44. Preacher, K. J., & Hayes, A. F. (2004). SPSS and SAS procedures for estimating indirect effects in simple mediation models. *Behavior research methods, instruments, & computers*, 36(4), 717-731.
45. Ravikumar, T., Rajesh, R., Krishna, T., Haresh, R., & Arjun, B. (2022). Changing customer mindset in adopting digital financial services during the COVID-19 pandemic: Evidence from India. *Banks Bank Syst*, 17, 58-71.

46. Ryu, H.-S. (2018). What makes users willing or hesitant to use Fintech?: the moderating effect of user type. *Industrial Management & Data Systems*, 118(3), 541-569.
47. Saad, M. A., & Fisol, W. N. M. (2019). Financial technology (FinTech) services: Analysis from the perspective of maqas. id al-Shariah. *Journal of Social Science and Humanities*, 2(6), 6-11.
48. Stewart, H., & Jürjens, J. (2018). Data security and consumer trust in FinTech innovation in Germany. *Information & Computer Security*, 26(1), 109-128.
49. Unnikrishnan, R., & Jagannathan, L. (2018). Do Perceived Risk and Trust affect Consumer Adoption of Mobile Payments? A Study of Indian Consumers. *South Asian Journal of Management*, 25(4).
50. Unit, E. I. (2018). *Global microscope 2018: the enabling environment for financial inclusion*.
51. Vasenska, I., Dimitrov, P., Koyundzhyska-Davidkova, B., Krastev, V., Durana, P., & Poulaki, I. (2021). Financial transactions using fintech during the COVID-19 crisis in Bulgaria. *Risks*, 9(3), 48.

Competing interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability

Data will be available on request.

Ethical approval

The authors confirm that all research was performed in accordance with ethical guidelines/regulations applicable when human participants are involved by the committee.

Informed consent

A written informed consent was obtained from all participants before conducting the survey.

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